

Explaining Kansei Design Studies

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Abstract

Within the last thirty years, Kansei studies have become an important field of research in Japan. More recently, foreign researchers have become more and more interested in understating the approach, despite the difficulties related to the cultural dimension of Kansei and Kansei studies. The aim of this research is to propose to westerners a clear description of what Kansei and Kansei studies are, and how it is different from classic western approaches on sensory or emotion design. Using this description of Kansei studies, a brainstorming has been organized to determine a list of keywords (KSK) used to structure and map comprehensively Kansei-related source of information. Moreover, a participative tool, called KanseiTako, is introduced. This tool aims at providing researchers, educators, and students, with an organized and useful set of knowledge sources to structure comprehensively the research field and the education in Kansei studies.

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Introduction

The term Kansei, in the way it is used in research activities, became popular at the beginning of the eighties, to characterize the change in consumption behavior in the rapid growth of Japanese economy. At this time of the Japanese intensive economical development, the design and the marketing efforts had to shift from a national consumption behavior following “rational principles”, to the one following more “individualized principles”. Design researchers associated this new consumption paradigm with the concepts of user’s mental images and mental preferences. As this link became stronger, the term Kansei appeared as a keyword for this new field of design in both academic and industrial worlds. The two major events pointing out the apparition of the term Kansei are the publication of two books on marketing (Kamei, 1983 and Fujioka, 1984), and the speech of Kenichi Yamamoto (President of Mazda Automotive Corporation), who used the term "*Kansei Engineering*" for the first time in 1986 during a presentation made at Michigan University, to relate the research works done by Kenichi Yamamoto and Mitsuo Nagamachi on “Emotional Engineering” (Nagamachi, 2001). Since then, the research field of Kansei has grown considerably: currently, the Japanese Society of Kansei Engineering (JSKE, 2007) gathers more than 1500 researchers and industrialists; numerous successful products have been designed thanks to Kansei approaches; a few international conferences on Kansei have been organized in Asia and in Europe; and Kansei has become one of the key vectors of the Japanese Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry (METI) to “*enhance people’s lifestyles and invigorate the economy*” (METI, 2007).

For some years, foreign researchers have been more and more interested by the great development of Kansei Engineering and of other fields of research related to Kansei (Kansei Information, Brain & Kansei...). However, the current international literature on Kansei does not provide clear enough description and research materials on Kansei and Kansei studies to be easily understood and adopted by the international design research community. Therefore, to help the international development of Kansei studies, it is important to describe not only the notion of Kansei, but also the structure and the practice of Kansei Studies. For both descriptions, the Japanese approach on this new field of research cannot be neglected since it is one of the key aspects in the structure of Kansei studies.

Hence, the global theme of the present research aims at describing Kansei and Kansei studies for their comprehensive and international understanding, including when some clarifications about the impact of Japanese mind and culture on Kansei studies are required. To do so, the notion of Kansei is first described. Thereafter, this description is used to characterize and to structure Kansei studies. This structuring is processed using a participative system called KanseiTako,

aiming at involving Kansei Studies community. Input, processes, and output are designed taking into account the previously determined descriptions. The long-term objective of KanseiTako is to map Kansei studies, in order to create a structure that links all actors and items of the Kansei study world, and to propose a comprehensive and adapted material for Kansei study education.

Kansei

There are only a few papers actually intending to describe comprehensively Kansei and Kansei research activities. Papers mentioning Kansei are numerous, but in most cases their description is approximate (when not clumsy) and are mostly limited to the field or the theme of the presented research work. Yet, some proposes an overview on Kansei and Kansei research, and are to be noticed in the Kansei research literature. The first noteworthy paper intending to describe Kansei was written by Harada in 1998 (Harada, 1998). Based on the proposition of 60 researchers working in the field of Kansei, he output a description of Kansei based on the following 5 points:

- Kansei is a subjective and unexplainable function.
- Kansei, besides its innate nature, consists of the cognitive expression of acquired knowledge and experience.
- Kansei is the interaction of intuition and intelligent activity.
- Kansei is the ability of reacting and evaluating external features intuitively.
- Kansei is a mental function creating images.

Harada's proposition appears to be too complex and not clear enough to clarify what Kansei is. However, his work is very important as it had been the first attempt to define Kansei, and had opened a path to go further in the description and the common understanding of Kansei.

Two other works can be noted here, because of the context they were produced in:

- During a visit at Delft University of Technology, in Holland, Lee introduced the notion of Kansei to western researchers (Lee, 2002). To do so, she simply showed the etymology of Kansei by showing and detailing the Chinese characters. This presentation, brilliant by its simplicity and its accessibility, has been quite successful for the introduction of Kansei outside of Japan, and is still currently used in many research presentations done in English.
- The work of Schütte et al. (Schütte, 2008) is one of the major European research works on Kansei Engineering. Mostly inspired from the work of Nagamachi (one of the creators of the Kansei Engineering), Schütte attempted to explain Kansei in a comprehensive way. His work has mainly consisted in explaining how Kansei and its mechanisms are considered in Kansei Engineering. He also pointed out the methods and the limits of the way user's Kansei is currently captured in Kansei Engineering (Schütte, 2008).

Other works and more detailed explanations can be found at (Levy, 2007). However, due to the importance of this concept for the present research, the resulting description will be briefly reminded here.

Describing Kansei

Based on the English literature on Kansei, a study towards a global description of Kansei has been processed and has output the following conclusion (visually described in Figure 1):

Kansei is usually described as a mental function, and more precisely as being a higher function of the brain. The literature indicates that:

- **Kansei process** gathers the functions related to emotions, sensitivity, feelings, experience, and intuition... (i.e. sensory qualities related functions (Clark, 1996)), including interactions between them.
- **Kansei means** are all the senses (sight, hearing, taste, smell, touch, balance, recognition...) and – probably – other “internal factors” (such as personality, mood, experience, and so on).
- **Kansei result** is the fruit of Kansei process (i.e. of these function processes and of their interactions). It appears to be **a unified perception providing a qualitative meaning and value of one's direct environment**. In other words, Kansei result is how one perceives qualitatively one's environment. Therefore, Kansei result is a synthesis of sensory qualities.

This description has a merit to provide information on the nature of Kansei process, of Kansei means, and of Kansei result. Also, an aspect of Kansei clarified in this description is the permanent and necessary link of Kansei with the perceptive field (Malherbe, 2000). Kansei cannot be considered without considering the senses, the mind, and the perceptive field.

Strictly speaking, the Kansei is only what has been characterized as Kansei process, i.e. a high function of the brain. Figure 1 intends to describe the Kansei process. In the perceptive field, a situated subject (represented by the ellipse) behaves. His/her senses (on the left side) perceive the environment. Senses' information is provided to the brain (the circle inside the body) to process Kansei. It is also highly probable – yet not proved – that many internal-body factors (such as body conditions, experience, personality, mood, and so on) influence Kansei. All this information providers are the tools (or means) for Kansei process. The nature of Kansei result is still mental (i.e. neither physiological nor behavioral). However, consequences of Kansei can be observed at a psychological, a physiological, and a behavioral level (on the right side). Also, it is to be noted that both the perceptive field and the body are dynamic elements. Therefore, this entire

description should not be thought as a linear pattern input/process/output: Kansei may be influenced by and may have influence on the mood, on the personality, on the experience, and on the environment (by the subject behavioral reaction).

Figure 1: A visual description of Kansei and Kansei Studies

Points of view on Kansei

From the description of Kansei, a few points can be stated:

- Kansei can be described as a holistic, concrete, and open sensory-mental model for human being. Senses, mental processes, and behaviors are all considered in the model to encounter human being in the perceptive field. Consequently, this model does have great interactions with models involving anything related to human beings and human activities (knowledge, preferences, communication, design...). These themes are often taken into consideration in Kansei research themes.
- The usual comment arguing that Kansei cannot be explained properly is considered as invalid by the authors. Whereas providing a complete, strict, and permanent definition of Kansei seems certainly irrelevant, a comprehensive and proper description of the concept, enabling anybody to comprehend it, was provided.

The actual specificity of Kansei, compared to western approaches on subjective human behavior, does not concern the concept of Kansei itself, but the project of Kansei studies. This argument can be introduced by Nisbett's suggestion: "*Confucianism has been called the religion of **common sense**. Its adherents are urged to uphold the Doctrine of the Golden Mean – to be excessive in nothing and to assume that between two propositions, and between two contending individuals, **there is truth on both sides**. But in reality, Confucianism, like Taoism, is less concerned with finding the truth [what Western philosophies are more concerned about (note from the author)] than with **finding the Tao – the Way – to live in the world**" (Nisbett, 2003, p.15). The differences are mostly inherent to the philosophical goal of cultures and by consequences to the global understandings and interests of the concepts by each culture. Whereas the intentions of western philosophical approach would be to determine the essence of Kansei (and related concepts distinctively) and to integrate it to a philosophical project, the actual intentions of Kansei studies are mostly to apprehend and to improve the effects of Kansei on human beings and on their environment (i.e. the world). In other words, the aim is not to understand the inside of the black box, but to know what (and how) we can do with it.*

Concerning research activity, this difference, related to culture and to philosophy, is the reason why Kansei studies may be hard to be comprehended, and therefore to be accepted by westerners: the project and the method are unfamiliar to western approaches.

Figure 2: Various views on Kansei

The key aspect that makes the method unfamiliar to western approaches is the possibility that two different positions can both be considered as true. Indeed, Kansei can be seen as a large and very complex system, that one cannot comprehend completely. Therefore, various individuals would have different views on the same system, due to the variability of experience, of knowledge, and of concerns (cf. Figure 2). However, these differences are not problematic, since there might be “truth on both sides” and may even be considered as a richness of the research field. An issue is raised if different points of view are conflicting, and the solution maybe found in a point where it makes sense for all, even if differences remain.

Kansei studies

Kansei Studies gather all the activities aiming together at measuring Kansei, and at taking benefit of this to improve the world.

As other high-functions of the brain, measuring Kansei (represented by the point A on Figure 1) cannot be done directly. What is observed is not Kansei but the causes and the consequences of the Kansei process (Nagasawa, 2002). Therefore, to determine some characteristics of Kansei, researchers often work on correlating different elements “surrounding” Kansei. Kansei can be measured only indirectly and partially, by measuring sensory activities (point 1 in Figure 4), internal factors (point 2), psycho-physiological and behavioral responses (points 4 to 6 – with a high risk of over-interpreting results output from psycho-physiological measurements), and finally environmental elements (point 3). In the scope of Kansei studies, sensory activities are measured by evaluating the impact of a specific sense stimulus on brain activity. Physiological measures are done by evaluating responses to specific external stimulations.

Kansei Design and related fields use knowledge developed by Kansei studies to create new designs. Kansei Engineering was the first, and so far the most successful design method created to involve some Kansei considerations in the design process. However, many other research methods have been developed, to increase and to improve Kansei considerations in design (Levy, *in printing*).

Kansei study Keywords

Approaches on Kansei studies are multiple, yet Kansei studies are one domain of study and require a common ground to structure all Kansei research activities. The visual description of Kansei (cf. Figure 1) is a representation of this ground, at least partially. However, for practical needs, this ground needs to be structured in order to map the fields of Kansei Studies, or any other kind of knowledge source. This map is structured using a set of markers thanks to which fields and sources of knowledge can be linked and related to others. These markers are called Kansei Study Keywords (KSK) and are defined as terms used to inventory any source of knowledge for Kansei studies and to relate these sources to each other.

The determination of KSK has been done by brainstorming sessions at the University of Tsukuba, Japan. As a raw material, the 240 keywords of the JSKE Spring Conference 2007 were used to determine the KSK. They seemed relevant to start, since they were picked by the conference presenters to describe their Kansei research paper. However, because the researchers had to determine them by themselves (a list of terms was not provided to the presenters), many

redundancies or Kansei-unrelated keywords may be expected. Moreover, because the conference may not have covered all the topics of Kansei studies, some KSK may have been missing from the original list. Therefore, a brainstorming was necessary to determine a relevant and usable list of KSK. Each brainstorming sessions were divided into four steps (cf. Figure 3):

- The description of each existing terms (e.g. The 240 JSKE keywords during the first session) – This step is important to make sure that the understanding of each term makes sense and is common to all participants;
- The terms were categorized to ease the global vision of the list. To help to this categorization process, the map (Figure 1) was used, and other categories (such as related disciplines) were added on the side of the map.
- In each category, each term was validated (relevant existence and relevant group) or eliminated.
- During the first three steps, the participants could take notes to propose the creation of new terms. The creation took place during the last steps, and each proposition was discussed and was concluded by an inclusion in one of the categories.

During the four steps, if one keyword was created or eliminated, a new session was planned a few days after, for participants to have time to have a rest.

Figure 3: Process of the brainstorming

SENSES	SENSE MEASUREMENT	Idea generation support Design Management Product Development Other management
Touch Sight Taste Hearing Smell Thermoception Nociception Equilibrioception Proprioception Other senses	Organism examination Chemical analysis Other sense measurement	MARKET
HUMAN CONDITION	HUMAN STATE MEASUREMENT	Intellectual property Branding Marketing Other management
Individual character Personality Experience Mood Body condition Other human condition	Behavior observation Personality inventory Projection Other human state measurement	ERGONOMICS
HUMAN CONSCIOUSNESS	INTRUSIVE MEASUREMENT	Ergonomics Usability Universal Design Other ergonomics
Conscious Unconscious Subconscious	Intrusive electric system Slice observation Chemical analysis Other intrusive measurement	DESIGN FIELDS
BRAIN PROCESSES	NON INTRUSIVE BRAIN MEASURING	City planning Architecture Product design Traditional craft Apparel Graphic design Information design Material engineering Other design
Learning Recognition Association Memory process Emotional process Creativity Intuition Impression Preference Evaluation Other brain processes	fMRI Brain blood flow Brain waves Other non-intrusive brain measurement	STATISTICS
BRAIN STRUCTURE	PHYSIOLOGICAL MEASURING	Univariable analysis Multivariable analysis Non-linear analysis Inference Other statistics
Brain development Hormones Synapse Systems Brain venal systems Other brain structure	Pupil Thermograph Muscle Skin electric resistance Pulse wave Heart rate Hormone Other physiological measuring	ROBOTICS
INTERNAL BEHAVIOR	BEHAVIORAL MEASUREMENT	Robotics behavior Robotic com Robotics recognition A.I. Other robotics
Physiological behavior Emotional behavior Autonomic nerve Other internal behavior	Meditative observation Hearing research Questionnaire Interview Behavior observation Eye tracking Motion tracking Other behavioral measurement	INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY
EXTERNAL BEHAVIOR	HUMAN SCIENCES	Internet Web 2.0 Mobile device RFID Interface Searching Software Other information technology
Non oral expression Oral expression Body expression Facial expression Action Other external behavior	Psychology Philosophy Cognitive science Sociology Verbal communication Non-verbal communication Disorder sciences Education Cultural engineering Other human sciences	ENTERTAINMENT
STIMULUS MEASUREMENT	MANAGEMENT	Games Media Other entertainment
Physical Measurement Chemical analysis Other stimulus measurement		

Table 1:KSK Keywords.

As a result, within four sessions, a list of 131 KSK, grouped in 23 categories, was output and was submitted in two languages (Japanese and English – Japanese version can be obtained on demand) for global validation (cf. Table 1). However, as KSK are markers of a permanently evolving domain, they will be reviewed regularly, taking into consideration the way they are used in practice. Therefore, the list proposed here is not definite, but provides a tool to structure the current field of Kansei Studies. Amongst other things, KSK are used as the core elements of the KanseiTako Project, aiming at mapping Kansei Studies.

KanseiTako project

KanseiTako project is an Internet-mediated knowledge community, which objectives are:

- To gather information about Kansei Studies sources of knowledge, and to structure and to link them using KSK.
- To enable researchers, educators, and students to access this information easily, and to use it efficiently for any type of purpose.

Figure 4: KSK links

The KanseiTako system proposes adapted but classic interface, using forms, for the (registered) users to input information. The sources of knowledge are of 7 types: Papers (articles, book sections...), books, events, fields of research, people (professors, researchers, industrialists...),

places (universities, exhibitions...), and web sites (cf. Figure 4). Using the KSK to categorize each source of information, a network is progressively structured between all the sources of information.

KanseiTako proposes also various tools to obtain information and to display it comprehensively and for further uses. Currently, KanseiTako outputs are of two types (cf. Figure 5):

- Classic (and rankable) files providing information about each source of knowledge and the access to discussion forum.
- A KanseiTraveler interface (currently in development): an intuitive interface enabling to travel around KanseiTako, and therefore to get through experience one's personal view on Kansei Studies. This interface is crucial because of the aforementioned characteristic of Kansei Studies.

Figure 5: KanseiTako structure

KanseiTako can be accessed at <http://pie.kansei.tsukuba.ac.jp> (registration required for use, to be opened to public).

Conclusion: implication for Kansei Studies

KanseiTako has been launched at the laboratory of Kansei Information Design of the University of Tsukuba for testing. However, KanseiTako use will be expanded internationally (from May 2008). As the system includes consistent information for Kansei studies, a digital and/or paper version of KanseiTako will be regularly published and distributed to registered users.

As a long-term objective, KanseiTako is expected to help the establishment of a global structure for Kansei studies, respecting the Japanese aspects of this field of research. The knowledge of this structure will be profitable:

- For researchers, to expand their network and to determine unreached aspects of Kansei studies. This is important, as it will also help the international strengthening of Kansei research community.
- For students, to expand their knowledge and their horizons on Kansei studies. Indeed, the exploration of KanseiTako will help them to structure their own points of view on Kansei and Kansei studies and to stimulate their curiosity and their ability to explore new lands of Kansei studies.
- For educators, to search and to provide any kinds of information or reference to students, and to determine the basic knowledge required by students to reach sufficient level in Kansei studies.

Education in Kansei Studies requires a common ground of knowledge, for all the future researchers and practitioners to be able to cooperate fully. That is a necessary condition for the development and the sustainability of Kansei studies. That is probably the first wish, and the first objective of the KanseiTako project.

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